

METHODS OF INTRODUCING CHILDREN TO NATURE IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract: The article provides information about the technology and methods of introducing children to nature for future educators. The tasks facing future educators to acquaint children with the world are described.

Keywords: animate and inanimate nature, environment, educators, skills and abilities, living organism, visual, practical, oral, observation, level of knowledge, portfolio, technology.

It would not be wrong to say that positive changes are taking place in education after the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence. Work is being done steadily in every aspect of community life. The basis of comprehensive education of children is to form a scientific outlook in them. Acquainting children with nature is of great importance in the implementation of this task. Man is an integral part of nature. Nature provides all the benefits necessary for human life. At the same time, a careful attitude towards nature is required. Otherwise, humanity can be left in the vortex of terrible losses. The main goal of education for children of preschool age is to educate the young generation as a healthy, intellectually mature, intellectually rich, well-rounded person in the formation of love for nature and mother nature, and to prepare them for school education. It is very important for the future educator to acquire theoretical and methodical knowledge in the formation of knowledge about nature for preschool children. Theoretical foundations, content of introduction to nature in pre-school educational organizations, organization of natural science works, nature corner, land areas and their types; forms, methods and means of introducing preschool children to nature will be closely introduced. With the correct organization and method of carrying out these forms of work, future educators will master the science of "Introduction of children to nature". The child directly perceives nature with the help of his senses. Therefore, it appears in front of him in various forms, sizes, colors, sounds, smells, and movements. This forms his emotional development and allows him to form the first clear ideas about nature, to form connections, to see, to understand the relationship and connection of natural phenomena (transition from visual to logical thinking). In order to introduce children to the world, the future educators-pedagogues have the following tasks: 1. Formation of children's primary knowledge system. The system of knowledge about nature includes knowledge about its objects and phenomena (their signs, properties), as well as connections and relationships between them. 2. Formation of labor skills and qualifications in children. Labor skills and qualifications acquired from childhood will not disappear, in the future they will become more complex types of work. 3. Formation of love for nature in children. Caring for nature implies the display of good deeds and actions when necessary, and for this children learn how to care for plants, their comfortable growth and they need to know how to create conditions for their development. In order to form such an attitude towards nature, it is of particular importance to acquire knowledge about living organisms and to be able to distinguish them

from inanimate objects of nature. The content of knowledge, skills and competences in introducing children to the surrounding world and nature: In a small group, children talk about separate objects of nature: natural material (sand, water, snow, ice) and its properties, the structure of plants (stems, leaves) knowledge, i.e. specific characteristics (stem, leaf, flower) and their need for moisture; it is necessary to familiarize with the appearance of animals (fish, birds, mammals) and their ways of movement and feeding.

Children will get acquainted with the polopons of some animals. Basic knowledge about the characteristics of the seasons is given. In the middle group, children's ideas about the properties and qualities of inanimate natural objects are expanded and clarified (for example, water is a transparent liquid, some things float in water, others sink; the properties of snow and water change depending on the air temperature). In a large group, the main task is to form children's knowledge about connections and relationships that exist in nature: about the needs of plants and animals depending on their living conditions and status, about the connections between certain organs and their functions. The main task in the preparatory group for school is to clarify and expand the regular changes of inanimate natural phenomena, and their subsequent systematization and generalization is the main issue. It is necessary to form opinions about the change of seasons, the lengthening (or shortening) of the length of day and night, regular changes in air temperature, and the nature of precipitation. Thus, by the end of preschool age, children acquire the basic system of knowledge about nature, which helps to develop mental activity and form a stable positive attitude towards nature. The complexity and variety of tasks require the educator-pedagogue to be able to use different methods and forms of working with children, which is related to a number of requirements and characteristics of different age groups. Forms of introducing preschool children to nature: activities, excursions, walks, work in the nature corner, work on the ground. Methods of introducing preschool children to nature: visual, practical, oral. 1. Demonstration method and its types. A visual method includes: observation, visual materials, technical aids or educational screen. Observation means purposeful, systematic perception of objects and phenomena of the surrounding world. Observation is purposeful, planned perception of objects and phenomena of the environment. Observation is a complex cognitive activity that involves perception, thinking, and speech. The child's experience, knowledge and skills are important in explaining the observed phenomenon. Constant observations in introducing children to nature are of great importance in developing their logical thinking and speech. About this K.D. Ushinsky says: "True human, intellectual speech consists in sound reasoning, and sound reasoning, as we have shown, comes from real and clear observations, not from anything else."

While organizing the observation of nature together with children, the future educator and pedagogue solves a number of tasks: forms children's knowledge about nature, teaches observation, develops observation, educates aesthetically. In the course of short-term observations, organized in order to form knowledge about the properties and qualities of objects and events, children learn to distinguish the shape, color, structure, spatial location, character of the surface of parts. A much more complex type of observation is used - long-term observations - in order to clarify knowledge about the growth and development of plants and animals, seasonal changes in nature, in which children have to compare the observed state of the object with the previous one. Depending on the level of knowledge of children, the teacher-pedagogue uses different types of observations. Observations are organized when

getting acquainted with plants and animals, with the weather, with the activities of adults in nature, during training, on excursions, walks and in the nature corner. At the beginning of the observation, especially if it is conducted for the first time, do not rush to give tasks or tasks to children. In the process of supervision, the educator-pedagogue uses various methods - questions, riddles, inspection of objects, comparison, game work activities. It is necessary to draw conclusions and come to some kind of decision only after the completed work. It is appropriate if it is given to strengthen the questions and assignments. Educators help children draw conclusions. The use of handouts in observations ensures high activity of children. The group of visual methods includes viewing pictures with children, showing slides and films. The use of these methods helps to solve various tasks, to clarify ideas and to systematize knowledge, to generalize, to create content of aesthetic perception. Pictures allow to see natural phenomena in more detail, to focus attention on this object for a long time, which is often not possible to do when observing nature directly due to the dynamism and changeability of nature. In addition, many events cannot be observed directly. Educational, eventful, object-oriented, as well as artistic pictures are used to introduce children to nature. Kindergartens use slides, movies, and TV films to introduce children to nature.

The educational screen forms the imagination of children about the dynamics of natural phenomena: the growth and development of plants and animals - the work of adults, and creates an opportunity to show the events of a long time in a short period of time. It is necessary to prepare children in advance to watch the film. For this purpose, talks, excursions related to the content of the film will be held, and book readings will be organized. Directly before the showing of the films, an introductory talk is held for the children, in which the children are given tasks that they should pay attention to while watching the film. After watching the film, a discussion will be held, focused on highlighting the important parts. For preschoolers, it is better to use a silent film. The educator tells their content. After the movie, it is recommended to have a special conversation with the little ones.

2. Practical method and its types. Various games are widely used in addition to observations made in order to expand imaginations and simple phenomena of nature. In these games, children gain sensory experience and creatively assimilate the acquired knowledge. Didactic, active and creative games are also used to introduce children to nature. In didactic games, children clarify, strengthen and expand their existing knowledge about things and events in nature, animals and plants. Many games teach children to generalize and categorize. Didactic games help to increase memory, attention, and observation, teach children to use their existing knowledge in new conditions, activate various mental processes, enrich vocabulary, and help children develop the ability to play together. To introduce children to nature, object-based, board-printed and oral didactic games are used. Games with objects are "Wonderful bag", "Fruits and roots", "Whose children are on this branch" and similar games played with leaves, seeds, flowers, fruits, vegetables. With the help of these games, children's imaginations about the characteristics and signs of objects with which they actively communicate are enriched. Object games are widely used, especially in small and middle age groups. These games allow children to use natural objects themselves, to compare them, and to note changes in some of their external signs. Object games include expanding the slightly complicated knowledge of all age groups, strengthening their thinking and developing their actions. Board games - Four Seasons, Babies, Fruits, Plants, Pick Leaves, Pair Pictures, etc.

These games help children to master the knowledge of plants, animals and inanimate natural phenomena, to form the skill of describing an object depending on the spoken word. The game is carried out together with the word, the word comes before the perception of the picture or is combined with the game. Such games are played with 5-6 children (can be grouped). Verbal games ("Why does he fly, run, jump", "In the water, in the air, on the ground", "It is not necessary", etc.) are very acceptable because no equipment is required. They are played in order to consolidate, generalize and systematize knowledge about the functions and actions of one or another body. These games develop attention, intelligence, speed of perception, and fluent speech. Action games are related to imitating the behavior of animals, their way of life, and some of them reflect inanimate natural phenomena. These are "Mother Hen and Chicks", "Cat and Mice", "Sun and Rain" and similar games. In creative games, children reflect the impressions received during training, excursions, daily life (work in a poultry factory, greenhouse, etc.), acquire knowledge about them, develop a creative attitude to work, and realize the importance of adults' work in nature. Child labor. Children's work in nature has great educational value. In the process of working, children develop relationships with nature. Work in nature educates children to be responsible for the given task. However, for this, children must acquire the necessary labor skills and understand the importance of their work. Work in nature creates favorable conditions for sensory education of preschool children. The teacher-pedagogue teaches children to achieve goals and results through work, to consider objects and sensory signs. Children's experience and experiment. Children love to experiment. The reason for this is that the scope of initial thinking is distinguished by the fact that they are visual-active and visual-image. The main advantage of using the experiment method is: children get real ideas about various aspects of the studied object, its relations with other objects and the environment; the child's memory is enriched, his thinking processes are activated; speech develops; develops a fund of mental skills and can apply it in practice; the child's emotional sphere, creative abilities develop, work skills are formed, health is strengthened due to the increase in the general level of physical activity; A preschool child learns the world around him through directed research (search) activities.

The more diverse the child's activities, the more new information he receives and, naturally, the scope of his thinking expands. 3. Oral method. Conversation. The use of oral methods solves several tasks. The value of a story about nature is determined by the fact that it solves certain educational tasks, is written taking into account the experiences and interests of children, and is intended for children of a certain age group. This is its advantage over reading fiction. Understanding the story is a very complex mental activity for children. The child should be able to hear and listen to the speech of adults, to understand it during the story, to actively imagine sufficiently vivid images based on verbal classification, to identify and understand the interdependence of events under the guardianship of the educator, and to determine and understand the news in the content of the story based on his previous knowledge. should be compared with The teacher-pedagogue defines all of these requirements for his story about nature. Vividness, imagery, and accuracy of the language are absolute requirements for the future teacher's story. For the story, the future educator uses a variety of material: personal observations of nature, stories of amazing people, essays and stories about natural phenomena, scientific materials. In introducing children to nature, the educator-pedagogue's story, reading art books about nature, and conversation are used. Using the oral method, the knowledge gained during observation and work in nature is clarified,

supplemented, summarized, and put into a system. Thus, the oral method allows the formation of knowledge that deviates from the scope of children's experience. Technologies used to get to know nature. Modern pedagogical technologies in preschool education are aimed at introducing state standards of preschool education, which determine new tools, forms, and methods used in pedagogical practice. ICT technologies of the "Information" age are well-studied and used in the professional activities of future pedagogues: - selection of illustrative materials and stands for decorating groups in classes. - selection of additional resources for training (presentations, cartoons, etc.). - exchange of experiences (kindergarten, websites created on the Internet), periodicals, familiarization with the developments of other pedagogues abroad. - interactive games. Project activity technology. This technology has a number of advantages: in-depth study of any topic of animate and inanimate nature and achievement of practical results. The method of project activity is successfully implemented and gives good results, especially when working with older children. This stage is characterized by the ability to start paying more attention, observation, analysis, synthesis, self-esteem, as well as the desire for cooperative activities. Classification of projects for getting to know the world: "Playful" - children's training, participation in group activities (games, folk dances, dramatization, various entertainment); "Excursion" is aimed at studying the problems related to the surrounding nature and social life. "Descriptive" is a classification in which children learn to convey their impressions and feelings verbally, artistically, gesturally; "Building-making" is aimed at creating a specific useful product, for example, assembling a birdhouse, creating a small garden with flowers planted in the form of a closed figure. Game technology. The concept of game pedagogical technologies includes a wide range of educational and innovative research methods and methods of organizing various pedagogical games in the form of pedagogical games, which differ from the points and matching game in general. This game In turn, as an elegant pedagogical result, it is clearly separated and characterized by a certain educational direction. The classification of educational games is based on several principles: games on physical (motor), intellectual (mental), labor, social and psychological issues.

Person-oriented technology. Person-centered technology is implemented in an evolving environment that meets the content requirements of new educational programs. In the developing space, there are attempts to create conditions for communication with children oriented to the individual, which allows the child to show his activity and fully realize himself. Within the framework of personal technologies, the principle of cooperation stands out as independent directions. Equality in the relationship of the teacher-pedagogue with the child, partnership in the "Adults - child" relationship system. The teacher-pedagogue creates the conditions for the developing environment of the children, prepares manuals, toys, gifts for holidays. Together, they determine various activities (games, work, joint projects, holidays, games - laughter, creating books). Children's portfolio technology. A portfolio is another type of technology that gives an opportunity to remember the child's personal achievements, successes, positive emotions, pleasant moments of his life in various activities. The process of creating a portfolio is a unique pedagogical technology. There are many portfolio options. The content of the sections is gradually filled in accordance with the capabilities and achievements of the preschool child. The portfolio may include several sections aimed at introducing children to nature: "I and nature"; "World of Nature"; "My good works"; "The world around us", "Winter decoration" (spring, summer, autumn); "How to protect nature?" and others. The

content of sections: pictures, drawings, drawing up schemes: "Take care of nature", "Rules of behavior in nature", "Cultivation of seeds", applications, herbarium, etc. The technological approach, new pedagogical technologies bring out the child's achievements and further guarantee their successful studies at school in the future. Any future teacher-pedagogue can become a creator of new technology without overcoming obstacles. Technology cannot be created without creativity. For a future teacher-pedagogue who has learned to work at a technological level, the cognitive process in his developing state is always in the main place. Everything is in our hands, so we should not miss opportunities.

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